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Prediction of Country Innovation Level

[PCIL]

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Prediction of Country Innovation Level project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [section name] section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Mirta Medak will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	preprocessed-data.csv	Structured text	comma separated value	513 KB	no
P2	putils.py	Source code	python file	11 KB	no
P3	global-innovation-index.ipynb	Other	Jupyter Notebook	1489 KB	no

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Global Innovation Index	KAPSARC Data Portal	public domain	no

R2	Global Innovation Index Dataset Schema	KAPSARC Data Portal	public domain	no
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1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

- The dataset R1 "*Global Innovation Index*" was re-used for this experiment, to predict Global Innovation Index from indicators collected in the dataset. The dataset "European innovation scoreboard 2021" (<https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/46934>) was considered, but discarded because it only contains data about European countries, and the R1 contains data about the whole world. The Global Innovation Index dataset features key indicators such as trademark applications, university rankings, GDP per energy use, and more. Insights on innovation, research, development, and technology world rankings across countries can be found. The Global Innovation Index (GII) aims to capture the multi-dimensional facets of innovation and provide the tools that can assist in tailoring policies to promote long-term output growth, improved productivity, and job growth. The GII helps to create an environment in which innovation factors are continually evaluated. It provides a key tool and a rich database of detailed metrics for 141 economies in year 2015. The dataset consists of 316,907 records. The theme of the dataset is demography, and it contains data about countries from the whole world. The dataset is temporal (contains data from 2013 until 2020) and it is updated annually. It is granulated by country, so for each year and for each country attributes such as "Indicator Name", "Indicator Description", "Indicator Unit", "Measure Name", "Measure Unit", and finally "Value" can be found. "Value" measures how much the specific indicator affects the global innovation index. The standardized description of the dataset's schema in JSON format is uploaded to properly describe the dataset.
- The project generates:
 1. P1: preprocessed dataset (derived from R1)
 2. P2: source code used for preprocessing and descriptive statistics
 3. P3: Jupyter Notebook that contains the entire workflow of the experiment, most importantly:
 - a. Data preparation and preprocessing
 - b. Descriptive statistics and data visualization
 - c. Feature analysis and reduction
 - d. Finding the optimal model and model training
 - e. Prediction and evaluation on the test set
 - f. Result interpretation and conclusions
- The re-used dataset (R1) is in .xlsx format. The source of R1 is KAPSARC Data Portal. How the data was collected unfortunately isn't a public information.

- The size of the R1 is 18.2 MB. After data preprocessing, the P1 dataset is generated, having a size of 513 KB. The dataset was preprocessed to a more intuitive table, which will be used by the models.
- The project does not generate other data, but it generates models that use the data mentioned above to predict the value of the Global innovation index (decimal value). A Jupyter notebook of the size 1,489 KB is produced. The notebook is documented with comments and explanations of the code. The results and outputs can be seen by running the Jupyter Notebook. No additional data is generated by the experiment.
- This is the link to the KAPSARC Data Portal: <https://datasource.kapsarc.org/pages/home/> where the dataset R1 can be found under the name “global-innovation-index-2015”. In order to see the download link one needs to create an account and log in to the Portal.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Officers of local/national governments might be interested in data created in this experiment. If the governments collect data on their country’s innovation level and its indicators, the use of the models created in this experiment is possible, in order to estimate which indicators are more important than the others. This can help funding decisions on national or local level.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository “TU Wien Research Data” that provides a persistent identifier (DOI) and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

Automated version control was used (Git).

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary) metadata standard is used to describe the reused raw dataset and the preprocessed dataset created in the experiment. This includes the

following attributes: when the dataset was created, when it was issued, its accrual periodicity, time period shown in the dataset, and which feature the granularity is based on. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

JSON object is created to describe the dataset schema, for both re-used dataset R1 and produced preprocessed dataset P1.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

All data is publicly available.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2024-04-30	TU Wien Research Data		CC0
P2	Open		2024-04-30	TU Wien Research Data		CC0
P3	Open		2024-04-30	TU Wien Research Data		CC0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it.

<https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

The data is accessible to all who have access to TU Wien Research Data Repository. There is no sensitive data and therefore no need for an access committee or other restrictions.

DOI for data R1, P1, P2, and P3: 10.70124/t6npa-fxb41

Metadata:

Metadata is published under the persistent identifier (DOI): 10.70124/bxxh2-4kb08.

The data will remain findable in the repository for 10 years. The metadata is guaranteed to remain findable for at least 15 years.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

The datasets schemas are written in standardized machine actionable format (JSON).

Metadata uses domain specific vocabulary as well as DCAT standard.

Data includes references to other data, for example, the metadata of the preprocessed dataset includes the reference to the dataset it was derived from.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC0 license, provided there are no data protection concerns.

Documentation needed to run the experiment is provided in the form of Jupyter Notebook that can be found in the repository.

The data produced will be useable by third parties because it is publicly available, accessible and well documented. Moreover, the preprocessed dataset is much more readable and intuitive than the raw dataset, hence the usability of it increases.

The following data quality checks will be done: peer review of data.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

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4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with [the work package leaders](#) being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager.

P1 (preprocessed-data.csv), P2 (putils.py), R1 (Global Innovation Index), P3 (global-innovation-index.ipynb), R2 (Global Innovation Index Dataset Schema) will be stored on Github public repository "Global-Innovation-Index". External storage will be used because TUfiles, server housing, TUOwnCloud, TUProCloud, and TUhost are all only for staff of TU Wien, so it is not possible for me to use them as a student. I tried to upload the project and data on TUGitLab, but it looks like i need a specific authorization to do so. That's why the only way for me to store the data during the research process is in my own Github repository, called global-innovation-index. The URL of the repository: <https://github.com/costasii/global-innovation-index>

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	reading only	reading only	reading only
P2	writing	reading only	reading only
P3	writing	reading only	writing
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P3	TU Wien Research Data	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

I do not and will not use other procedures for data management.